

Rate of Δv Determination for Near Earth Asteroids

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10 December 2014

Received _____; accepted _____

ABSTRACT

The best near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) candidates for observation are those with low Δv as it is these that are best suited for unmanned, manned, scientific, and commercial expeditions. The majority of NEAs being discovered are small and dim, having a diameter of less than 100 meters and an absolute magnitude of $H \geq 22$. In approximately one week, the magnitudes are so faint that follow-up photometry, spectroscopy, and astrometry are no longer possible except with the largest telescopes. This requires follow-up observations to be done within days of an asteroid’s initial discovery. Given the large number of asteroids being discovered annually and the short timespan when they are bright enough for observations, only the best low Δv candidates can be selected for follow-up observations. We used archival observation data of 200 representative asteroids from the Minor Planet Center (MPC) and the Find_Orb orbit determination software from Project Pluto to determine the speed at which orbital parameters converge on a Δv solution. Based on the data, after three days of observations, 95% of NEAs converged to within 10% precision.

INTRODUCTION

Near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) are asteroids whose orbits bring them close to the Earth. Often, their orbits intersect or cross the Earth’s orbit. NEAs are of interest for a variety of different reasons. Scientifically, asteroids provide insight and clues into the formation of the Solar System from both a compositional and dynamical perspective and can allow us to investigate the origins of our Solar System. In addition, NEAs are of much interest when it comes to planetary defense. Finding and studying NEAs that could impact Earth would enable proper actions and measures to be taken. NEAs are also of interest for resource exploitation. Asteroids contain resources that could be mined and extracted for a variety of

different purposes.

Approximately 1000 new NEAs are being discovered every year. The majority of these are small and dim. (Galache et al. 2014) These NEAs typically have a diameter of less than approximately 100 meters and a magnitude of $H \geq 22$ where H is the apparent magnitude of the asteroid should it be observed at zero phase angle while 1 AU from both the observer and the Sun. As such they are fairly faint at their initial discovery ($V > 20$) even if discovered during the peak of their magnitude. The magnitudes of these asteroids fall off fairly rapidly, by around 0.5 magnitude after 1 week and 3.5 magnitude after a month. (Galache et al. 2014) Thus, after a short amount of time, high-precision follow-up photometry, spectroscopy, and astrometry are no longer possible except with the largest telescopes.

This rapid fading requires most follow-up observations to be done quickly, preferably within days of an asteroid’s initial discovery. Given the large number of asteroids being discovered and the short timespan available for observations, only the best candidates should be selected for follow-up observations.

A major criterion for selecting NEAs of interest is their Δv value. Δv represents the change in velocity needed to move from one orbit to another. Specifically, in our case, the Δv is the change in velocity between low-Earth orbit and the NEA orbit. $(\Delta v)^2$ is the energy per unit mass required. Hence, Δv is also a measure of the amount of propellant needed to move between orbits. A low Δv indicates an asteroid whose orbits is easier to access. As such, NEAs with low Δv are the best candidates as it is these that are best suited for autonomous, human, scientific, or commercial expeditions. The OSIRIS-REx mission, slated for a 2016 launch, is destined for 101955 Bennu, an NEA asteroids with a Δv of approximately 5.1 km/s. (Hergenrother et al. 2014) In 2005, the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency’s (JAXA) Hayabusa spacecraft landed on 25143 Itokawa, an NEA with a Δv of approximately 4.6 km/s. Hayabusa 2 was recently launched and is set to rendezvous

with (162173) 1999 JU3 which has a Δv of 4.7 km/s.¹ (Ishiguro et al. 2014) As shown in Figure 1 from M. Elvis et al. 2011, the majority of NEAs have Δv values that are larger than the target NEAs of previous as well as planned missions. As such, low- Δv NEAs are of particular interest for mission planners.

Fig. 1.— Distribution of Low-Earth Orbit to Near-Earth Asteroid’s Orbit Δv . (M. Elvis et al. 2011). Recent missions went to NEAs with Δv ranging from 4.6 km/s to 5.1 km/s; these are relatively rare.

Determining Δv requires the determination of the orbital elements of the asteroid. This includes the semi-major axis, eccentricity, as well as the inclination of the orbit. We wish to determine the amount of observations needed for a precise Δv solution to be reached in order to prevent the misuse of time and resources observing an asteroid for which Δv was too large to be of interest. This would allow a more efficient determination of which asteroids should be prioritized for follow-up spectroscopy or other observations.

¹ Δv values for asteroids were retrieved from the MPC.

METHODS

Observational data from 200 NEAs was processed by the a pipeline containing Python scripts and a compiled C++ program designed to solve for orbits. Observations are iterated over such that convergence behavior can be observed.

Data Retrieval Observational data was first obtained from the IAU Minor Planet Center (MPC)². The MPC database contains observations for asteroids, as well as comets and provides a method of accessing the data. Using a series of Python functions, observational data from 200 asteroids discovered in the Catalina Sky Survey³ was extracted. The set of NEAs were chosen to be fairly recent. Nearly all of the NEAs were discovered after 2010, with the farthest back being one discovered in 2003. For each asteroid, a file is downloaded, containing a list of all observations made. Each observation record includes, the date, time, Right Ascension, Declination, observed magnitude and band, as well as observatory. We also downloaded the final orbit parameters determined by the MPC for each NEA.

Processing of Raw Data In order to see how the orbital parameters change as more observations are included in the calculations, a Python script was written that cumulatively adds observations one night at a time to the parameter and Δv determination process. A second Python script achieves the same one observation at a time.

Since a “night” of observation is ambiguous given the various observatories around the world that provide observations, a night of observation must be defined carefully. A night of observation is defined to be the 24 hours after the time of the initial discovery.

²<http://www.minorplanetcenter.net>

³http://www.lpl.arizona.edu/css/css_sss_newdisc.html

Find_Orb The data is then processed by the Find_Orb orbit determination software.⁴ Developed as part of Project Pluto, Find_Orb uses the MPC data and calculates the orbital elements for that object based on the given data. This result includes orbital parameters needed to determine Δv the semi-major axis (a), inclination (i), and eccentricity (e).

Δv Calculation Using these orbital parameters (a, e, i), the Δv is calculated with the Shoemaker-Helin methods of Shoemaker and Helin (1979). A Python script implementing the Shoemaker-Helin equations was written to implement the method. This method of calculating Δv is only approximate. (Shoemaker et al. 1979) However, as accurate methods require substantial super-computer resources and given that the focus of this project is convergence, high accuracy is not required.

RESULTS

The behavior of orbit solutions for individual asteroids can be see in Figures 2 and 3. For the case of one particular low Δv asteroid: 2011 BO59, Figure 2 shows the convergence of the orbital parameters of 2011 BO59 as additional observations are included. Figure 3 shows the convergence of the orbital parameters of 2011 BO59 as additional nights of observation are included. The final orbital parameter values from Find_Orb are consistent with those provided by the MPC.

Running the observation for 200 asteroids allowed the determination of this behavior for the sample.

Normalized and logarithmic plots of Δv convergence for each asteroid was produced and overlaid (Figure 4). After 2 nights of observations, the majority of the NEAs in the sample have settled to a reliable Δv value. By the 7th night of observation (after a week), only one NEA had a Δv uncertainty larger than 20%. This plot was reduced to Figure 5

⁴http://www.projectpluto.com/find_orb.htm

Fig. 2.— Values of orbital parameters for 2011 BO59 vs. number of observations. For this asteroid, the parameters converged on a solution after approximately 13 individual observations. Δv value provided by the MPC is shown by the red arrow.

Fig. 3.— Values of orbital parameters for 2011 BO59 vs. nights of observations since discovery. For this asteroid, the parameters converged on a solution after approximately three days of observations. Δv value provided by the MPC is shown by the red arrow.

for further analysis.

The number of nights of observations needed for the orbit parameters to settle to 5% was determined as well. An error of 5% is small enough such that low- Δv can fairly confidently be determined. A larger error ($\approx 10\%$) would make it possible for an asteroid which is not low- Δv to be classified as such and vice-versa. Figure 6 shows the raw distribution of the number of observations and nights of observations needed respectively to reach 5% precision of Δv . The same data is presented as cumulative histograms as shown in Figures 7 and 8. This shows that 50% and 90% of NEAs have Δv determined to 5% after 15 and 54 observations and 2 and 6 days, respectively.

DISCUSSION

The orbital parameters of the sample NEAs allowed us to investigate whether there was correlation between the a , e , and i orbit parameters and the convergence rate of Δv . Figure 9 shows there was no relation between the orbital parameters and the number of nights needed to converge on a Δv solution. In other words, the number of nights needed for the convergence of Δv is independent of the type of orbit itself. As such, we can reasonably expect all NEAs to be applicable under this project.

Based on Figure 5, we see that by the first night of observation, 1- σ (68%) of NEAs are within 10% of the true Δv values, and less than 5% after 2 nights. By the third night of observation, 2- σ (95%) of NEAs are within 10% fractionals. For 3- σ of NEAs, more than 10 nights of observations are needed. It appears that a substantial deviation occurs with 3- σ of NEAs. This is likely the result of the inclusion of NEAs with odd behavior into the fit. This data is summarized in Table 1.

Of the 200 NEAs, several NEA's convergence behavior deviated from that of the rest. In particular, the Δv convergence of 2010 MF1, 2011 AG5, 2011 QD48 exhibited odd convergence behavior. Whereas most exponentially decayed toward a solution and settled

Fig. 4.— The logarithmic and normalized plots Δv vs. nights for the 200 asteroids are overlaid.

Percent of Population	Precision after 1 night	Precision after 2 nights	Precision after 3 nights
1- σ (68%)	5%	2%	<1%
2- σ (95%)	39%	15%	6%
3- σ (99%)	74%	38%	29%

Table 1: Precision of Δv value for a percentage of the NEA set after nights of observation as based off of Figure 5.

down to remain there, 2010 MF1 and 2011 AG5 deviates from the solution it arrived at. While in both cases, the addition of more observations would return back to the solution, these perturbations may ultimately extend the period of time projected to be needed to arrive at a stable Δv solution.

In 2011 QD48, the Δv solution was reached after approximately 10 nights of observations, and remained so for more than 70 nights of observations afterwards. The most recent sets of observations, however, led to an extremely large deviation as shown in Figure 10. Perturbations such as this also occur that deviate the Δv value temporarily. This extends the period of time before a solution is attained. Increasing the sample size to several thousand, or perhaps even all, NEAs would likely dampen the affect of outliers such as this.

CONCLUSION

Using the archival data of 200 recently detected NEAs, the convergence of their Δv values on a solution was studied as a function of both days since discovery and number of observations since discovery. After 1 night of observations, 68% of asteroids converged to within approximately 5% precision of the final Δv value. After the second night, 95% converges to approximately 15% of the final value. After the third night, 95% of NEAs converge to within 10% and 68% converged to the final Δv value. As such, the determination of Δv can be done for the majority of the population to within 10% precision after three nights of observations. Typically follow-up spectroscopic or other detailed observations of confidently low Δv NEAs can then begin on the fourth night following discovery. The existence of a few outliers present slight complications to this result. Since this time is within the period of which most NEAs are still bright enough to observe in detail, this timescale allows for prioritizing asteroids for follow-up observations.

Fig. 5.— n - σ

Fig. 6.— Raw Histograms of Observations and Nights of Observations to converge to 5% precision for Δv , respectively.

Fig. 7.— Cumulative Histogram (Observations)

Fig. 8.— Cumulative Histogram (Nights of Observations)

Fig. 9.— Plots of Nights to 5% Δv Precision vs. Orbital Parameters - There is no notable correlation between the number of nights and the parameters.

Fig. 10.— Normalized Plot of 2011 QD48. The most recent observations led to a large departure from the reached solution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to Martin Elvis for his invaluable advisement and guidance throughout this project. Thanks to Jose Luis Galache for insight into writing the Python code and Sukrit Ranjan for his computing power as well as the Shoemaker-Helin equation Python function. Thanks to Charlie Conroy for keeping us on task.

REFERENCES

- Elvis, M., McDowell J., Hoffman, J. A., Binzel, R. P. Ultra-low delta-v objects and the human exploration of asteroids. In. *Planetary and Space Science*, 59 (2011), pp.1408-1412
- Galache, J.L., Beeson, C.L., McLeod, K.K., Elvis, M., 2014. The Need for Speed in Near-Earth Asteroid Characterization.
- Hergenrother, C.W., Barucci, M.A., Barnouin, O., Bierhaus, B., Binzel, R.P., Bottke, W.F., Chesley, S., Clark, B.C., Clark, B.E., Cloutis, E., dAubigny, C.D., Delbo, M., Emery, J., Gaskell, B., Howell, E., Keller, L., Kelley, M., Marshall, J., Michel, P., Nolan, M. Rizk, B., Scheeres, D., Takir, D., Vokrouhlick, D.D., Beshore, E., Lauretta, D.S., 2014. The Design Reference Asteroid for the OSIRIS-REx Mission Target (101955) Bennu. arXiv:1409.4704
- Masateru Ishiguro et al. 2014. Optical Properties of (162173) 1999 JU3: In Preparation for the JAXA Hayabusa 2 Sample Return Mission. *ApJ* 792 74. doi:10.1088/0004-637X/792/1/74
- Shoemaker, E. M., Helin, E. F., Wolfe, 1978. NASA CP-2053 pp.245-256